

Sustainable Victoria 2030:

Educational Campaign Role in Shaping Victorians' Behavior on Waste Management to Prepare for the Circular Economy Transition

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Introduction

In PART B, the white paper addresses the lack of evidence identified from PART A by using the rapid review to investigate the existing evidences. The Sustainable Victoria 2030 (SV2030) policy's theme of circular economy is based on public opinion surveys with limited peer-reviewed evidence on the effectiveness of the campaigns, “Behaviour Change and Education” focus areas of SV2030, such as *ResourceSmart Schools*, and *Love Food Hate Waste*. The strategy does not provide enough data and mechanisms of these initiatives to ensure long-term behavioral change through educational initiatives for the successful transition to the circular economy.

To address this gap, this review aims to investigate the existing evidence on the effectiveness of educational campaigns on waste management to ensure households and schools transition to the circular economy. The research question is structured using the PICO framework detailed in table 1 (Livoreil et al., 2017). The research question is: **“Are educational behaviour change campaigns on waste management effective in promoting practices for households and schools that support circular economy transition?”**.

Two main concepts are addressed in this review, namely educational behavior change and circular economy. In SV2030, educational behavior change refers to the spread of messages and knowledge. As one of the 10 activities, the behavior change campaign aims to influence a more conscious consumerism (Sustainability Victoria, 2020). The research question links closely to two main resources mentioned in SV2030, which are people and materials. Then, the second main concept, “circular economy”, refers to the shift from the linear economy model of “buy, use, and dispose” to “avoid, minimise, reduce, and reuse” with emphasis on circulating waste within the economy. Therefore, educating the community to change their behaviors is a crucial piece of the puzzle in preparing them for the transition to this new economic model.

The SV2030 strategy has mentioned incorporating best practices, research, and knowledge to maximize the behavioral campaign. Without specific evidence to guide on what works and what fails, SV2030 could risk an essential part of its successful implementation. Therefore, this rapid review will synthesize findings from various educational and awareness campaigns to act as navigation for SV2030 to design and deliver an impactful initiative. The findings and recommendations of various research around the world could fill in the critical gap of knowledge to unlock effective campaigns in waste reduction, ensuring a smooth transition toward a circular economy.

Review Protocol

This review uses the rapid review methodology, following the PRISMA framework (Page et al., 2021). As a streamlined version of a systematic review approach, a rapid review is used due to its practicality by providing a structured approach to synthesising existing evidence, while balancing the time and resources constraint (Cook et al., 2017). Shortcuts taken in this review, such as narrow database coverage and moderate confidence level in the review process, could lead to a risk of biases (Cooke et al., 2023). These trade-offs are justified to fit with the purpose of the review for this policy recommendation for SV2030.

Search Strategy

Guided by the PICO framework, the search is structured to ensure clarity and reproducibility by using Boolean operators and search terms (Livoreil et al., 2017). The search terms were created by identifying search terms and synonyms describing the PICO elements (See Table 1). An additional context of waste is included to fully reflect the proposed research question. Web of Science and Scopus are the two main databases due to its relevance of rich multidisciplinary sources, which is crucial for sustainability science relevant for SV2030 (Livoreil et al., 2017). Moreover, these two databases are also accessible through the Monash Library subscription.

Table 1: PICO and Boolean Search Terms

PICO	Search terms (Boolean operators)
Population: Households and schools in waste generation and disposal	"school*" OR "house*" OR "community*"
Intervention: Educational behaviour campaigns on waste management	"educat*" OR "aware*" OR "initiate*" OR "program*" OR "campaign*" OR "project*"
Comparison: No intervention or other intervention than behaviour campaigns	"behav* change" OR "social change*"
Outcome: Changes in behaviors to be prepared for the circular economy	"circular economy" OR "closed loop" OR "sustain*"
Additional Context	"waste" OR "waste manag*"

Screening Process

This rapid review aims to use evidence from peer-reviewed articles to ensure the best knowledge and recommendations are extracted. The search and review process is done by only one researcher throughout the whole process. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are summarized in the table 2. The publication types and languages were used as filters during the search, while the other criteria were used during the first and second screening processes detailed below. These criteria were used due to the limited time, the reviewer's language limitations, and relevant studies from other countries and within Australia to create informed outcomes of the process campaign for the SV2030 implementation.

Table 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Publication Types	Peer-reviewed journal articles	Grey literature, conference abstracts, reports, and others
Language	English	Other languages

Population	Households, schools, or communities related to waste management all over the world	Others, like entrepreneurs, industrial sectors, etc.
Intervention	Educational or awareness campaign, behavior change-related programs	Others, including application, monitoring tools, and other interventions
Outcomes	Result of change in narrative or quantitative behavior change, and linked to circular economy implications	Other irrelevant studies

Table 3: PRISMA 2030 Flow Diagram

From the initial search, 119 results were obtained (69 from Web of Science, 50 from Scopus). After the automatic duplication removal using EndNote (n=21) and manual duplication screening (n=10), 31 duplicates were removed. The remaining 88 unique research papers were screened through the title abstract screening process, in which 55 papers were irrelevant, including health and tourism campaigns. The second screening process excluded another 18 papers due to the lack of behavioral outcomes,

a different target population, and a misaligned methodology. The final 15 studies were included in the collation table for evidence synthesis (See Table 3).

Data Extraction

With the 15 studies included, a collation table and CASP scorecard table are used (CASP, 2024). In these two tables, the extracted information includes the bibliography information, study design, sample characteristics, intervention types, common behavioral outcomes, contextual factors, and implications for future interventions. Moreover, studies quality, methodology clarity, results, and accuracy are also measured using the scorecard of “yes, no, and unsure”. This process provides a clear and transparent comparison across diverse studies, especially in environmental studies (Cooke et al.,2023). With this protocol of extraction, the rapid review process acknowledges the limitations and ensures the replicability and transparency.

Results

The results of the evidence synthesis from 15 high-quality studies provide a broad range of study scopes, study methods, and demographics (See Appendices). The interventions included in this research are educational institution-based campaigns, experiential learning, and community waste reduction programs, with inclusion of a specific food waste program. The findings of these studies are captured in four main themes, including the overall effectiveness, context and structural factors, and implications from schools and household dynamics.

Overall Effectiveness of Educational Campaigns

The interventions in these studies show both qualitative and quantitative results on the positive impacts on behavior in waste management. In the food waste reduction campaign by Yazdankhah et al. (2020), it is reported that 50% household waste was reduced after the implementation of educational information through posters, pamphlets, training, and messages. Similarly, another study with a targeted cafeteria

program also reported a reduction of 26-28% in waste among universities (Alattar & Morse, 2021). Moreover, there are various studies that emphasize co-design and experiential (on-hand) learning to increase the recycling knowledge and action within the community (Chenier et al., 2024; Tong et al., 2018). The on-hand practices and strong community support are also proven to be effective for school behavior change programs (Altassan, 2023; Benyam et al., 2018; Goldman et al., 2021).

Context and Structural Factors

While the results of these studies report a positive influence on behavior change, a few studies highlight the importance of infrastructure, targeted campaigns, and incentives as motivators. One of the recurring points is the physical infrastructure, like the availability of bins and recycling service (Chikowore, 2021; Cuellar et al., 2025; O'Dwyer et al., 2022; Tangwanichagapong et al., 2017). For example, the container deposit schemes in South Australia reported 68% of uptake, and could achieve better results with more containers around the communal area. Moreover, Sahoo et al. (2024) suggested that specific target outreach campaigns are more effective. Lastly, the use of incentives as motivation is agreed in several research studies (Altassan, 2023; Chenier et al., 2024; Gibovic & Bikfalvi, 2025; Sahoo et al., 2024; Tangwanichagapong et al., 2017; Tong et al., 2018).

Schools and Household Dynamics

Another finding is that the influence of agents of change, social norms, and collaboration in school and household settings could increase the effectiveness of the initiatives. Waste education and behavior change campaigns conducted at school provide support to households through engagement between family members by the teacher and student as agents of change (Altassan, 2023; Goldman et al., 2021). Moreover, the social interaction of households and communities also reinforces and increases awareness and accountability between neighbors (Cuellar et al., 2025; Gibovic & Bikfalvi, 2025; Krawczyk et al., 2025; Tong et al., 2018). Effective tools like

Community-Based Social Marketing (CBSM), waste education called the SWAPS program, and “Plastic Detectives” are some of the examples that exhibit the high adoption of behavior change through collaboration and visual demonstration to the community (Cole & Fieselman, 2023; Chenier et al., 2024; Krawczyk et al., 2025).

Limitations of Rapid Review

This rapid review is done through some shortcuts taken in the search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and methodology in the selection of research papers (CASP, 2023). Overall, these decisions create a potential bias that may affect the comprehensiveness and rigorous synthesis of all available evidence to answer the research question (See Table 4).

Table 4 Shortcuts and biases adopted from Virginia Commonwealth University (VCU) library

Rapid Review Shortcut	Potential Bias/Issue/Limitation
One reviewer performing the search and data extraction	Selection bias: lack of verification and risk of errors, and subjectivity
Exclusion of grey literature, conference abstracts, reports, and others	Publication bias: potentially omits other evidence from these excluded sources
Limited to the English language	Language bias: potentially omits evidence of similar studies from non-English sources
Limited to search saturation of 15 papers	Sampling bias: omit additional relevant evidence
Number of databases used (Web of Science and Scopus)	Selection bias: risk of excluding essential evidence in other databases
One researcher is conducting a results synthesis	Confirmation bias: risk of unconscious bias toward confirming the researcher’s pre-existing belief
Rich in qualitative data from the selected study	Measurement bias: risk of errors in data extraction, leading to subjective interpretation of data
Excluding older articles (no article older than 2013)	Temporal bias: overlook older publications and miss out on older evidence (Livoreil et al., 2017)

Conclusion

This rapid review synthesized evidence from 15 peer-reviewed articles to provide evidence on the effectiveness of educational behavior change campaigns in waste management to support the circular economy transition. From the findings, the different interventions are consistent in positive change on education and awareness in improving waste reduction behaviors. It is also noted that a combination of collaborative effort, community participation, and infrastructure at both physical and policy levels can enhance the effectiveness of these campaigns. Therefore, the SV2030 strategy could use the successful initiatives and tools of these findings to design its educational behavior change programs. Ensuring clear community support mechanisms, strong partnerships with schools and local communities, and targeted campaigns are the key to a successful delivery of the proposed activities in SV2030. Incorporating these behavioral change campaign elements will prepare Victorians to engage in the new circular economy.

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Appendices

AT3b Collation Table

Lead Author Name	Year Published	Study Design	Sample & Population	Data 1	Data 2	Data 3	Data 4	Study Quality	Comments
Alattar, M.A. & Morse, J.L.	2021	Mixed Methods	University students (200-300 student daily cafeteria) 174 survey respondents	26-28% reduction in food waste	Improved attitudes/behavioral intentions (Positive)	High knowledge of the population studied lead to little change in behaviors		High Quality	Strong evidence to support change in behaviors for university students.
Allassan, A.	2023	Other	Field observation, literature review, and simulation analysis to align to Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 with Ten schools from Riyadh's districts	Benefit of using experiential learning on engagement waste reduction by training and composting to rehabilitate the ecological system	Students as agent of change for wider spread of waste reduction and recycling practices into household	Factors to ensure effective framework implementation: synergy of stakeholder engagement, resource allocation, tailored education, incentives, continuous monitoring, student leadership, strategic partnerships, adaptability, comprehensive training, and public support		High Quality	
Benyam, A., Kinnear, S. & Rolfe, J.	2018	Qualitative	17 Community members in Focus Group Discussion (FGD)	Education ranks 2nd as policy options to address Domestic Food Waste	Emphasis on the role of FW education confirms the relevance of factoring in cognitive elements in addressing undesirable food utilization behaviours	Follow up, commitment and minitance is need to ensure effective desired outcome	Also addressing young audience on the educational campaign	High Quality	Qualitative response on the solutions
Chenier, K.A., Englebretson, E., James-Barry, J.A., Rigsby, A.N., Rodolfich, A.E., McQueen, E.P. & Sparks, E.L.	2024	Other	5000 people recieved training on 4-level module on waste education called SWAPS program	Incentives to be used by participants in their actions	Suggest Train-the-Trainer Model for future program implement for wider reach	SWAPS should lead to a more-educated and engaged public and behavioral changes that reduce waste and mismanaged waste.		High Quality	4-level educational campaign module
Chikwore, N.	2021	Quantitative	3200 households aged 18 years to 74 years in a survey	34% of the respondents recommend the need for environmental education programs to promote sustainable waste disposal practices	residents lack information on the effects of burnt waste on their health, which should be included in environmental awareness programs.			High Quality	
Cole, E.J. & Fieselman, L.	2013	Mixed Methods	Survey and data (pre-test, Post test)	74% reported yes on behavioral change after the campaign	long-lasting effect of the campaign need patience and long term effects	CBSM is one of the model to explain environmental knowledge and what causes people to exhibit pro-environmental behaviors		High Quality	
Cuellar, J.A.A., Puerto-Rojas, E., Correa-Galindo, S.N. & Puentes, M.C.S.	2025	Mixed Methods	Questionnaire, Facilitated discussion and Geospatial data of 293 resident in colombia	Most influential factor hinder waste separation is the negative consequences of waste	Contextual Barriers include awareness campaign, bin proximity, and coordination of interventions	Economical benefits can link to willingness, but knowledge and social pressure is a more influential factors	Consider dyanmic awareness campaign with clear visual and message, work with influencer and utilize digital marketing for effectiveness	High Quality	Strong evidence of the research process to design the recommendation intervention.
Gibovic, D. & Birkalvi, A.	2025	Other	Case study of RECICLOS in using social innovation to combine with technology in waste management solution	Awareness and Education: informed citizen on the benefits and impact	Behavioral campaign: nudging technique, reward and social norms	Social innovation has the power to transform citizens' behaviour and shape the future of recycling by increasing awareness, promoting behavioural change, fostering community engagement, leveraging technology, advocating for policy changes, encouraging sustainable consumption and promoting circular economy principles.		High Quality	RECICLOS, a pioneering project centred on augmenting public awareness and incentivising recycling behaviour, stands as an example of social innovation within the waste management domain
Goldman, D., Akaher, I. & Aram, I.	2021	Qualitative	150 observations and 10 interviews with teachers at primary and pre school	Having educator as a social change agent	Hand-on experience and visit at the facility leading to cognitive and emotional components for long-term effect	Behavior change is beyond information sharing	TSL: head (cognitive), hands (experiential), and heart (emotional)	High Quality	transformative sustainability learning (TSL): School-focus initiative that could help shift consumerism and lifestyle change for waste prevention, and setting example for students

Krawczyk, A., Salas, B. O. & Grodzinska-Jurczak, M.	2025	Mixed Methods	Survey, reflection and monitoring with student, teacher and community members on "Plastic Detective" and "Citizen Science"	Reported of willingness to reduce plastic waste and try out alternatives	Citizen science proven as effective, but lack data to back up waste measurement	"The study suggested that individuals are more likely to adopt cloth bags if they see others in their social circle using them."	Confirm another social pressure for behavior change	High Quality	CS can play an important role to bridge the gaps of scientists, policymaker and researchers.
O'Dwyer, C., Zaman, A. & Breadwell, J.K.	2022	Quantitative	414 Survey respondent in Perth	2/3 (68%) are using the CDS, high uptake	Social Media, Word of mouth, and online ads are main contributors to the CDS exposure	Skepticism and trust toward the recycling process is the main barriers to more uptake	Suggestion to increase the variety of containers, location proximity of the containers, and education regard the CDS.	High Quality	Highly applicable for the CDS scheme in SV2030, and aligned with other research to improve the uptake. Contradicting to other research an education level and income level are not associated with the uptake of CDS
Sahoo, K.C., Kaiyanasundaram, M., Singh, S., Soni, R., Parashar, V., Pathak, A., Lundborg, C.S., Rosta, K., Atkins, S. & Diwan, V.	2024	Qualitative	Semi-structured interview with 25 respondents on perspective and experience of project team in waste management in India	Strong emphasize on education and awareness on benefits and consequences of waste for success among team member and community	Creative knowledge discrimination tools like songs, social media, local artists utilized for broad outreach	Incentives are also offered for motivation	Designing campaign needs to be tailored to the target group for effectiveness	High Quality	Main recommendations: incentivizing source segregation through reduced disposal fees and taxes, enhancing education and awareness campaigns, investing in infrastructure, fostering trust between service providers and residents, and conducting regular monitoring and evaluation
Tangwanichagapong, S., Nilivattananon, V., Mohanthy, B. & Visvanathan, C.	2017	Mixed Methods	waste audits, waste composition analysis, field observations, key informant interviews and fieldwork records	3R program show awareness and knowledge difference but no change in behavior	3 barriers to good recycling practices were inadequate recycling infrastructure, inconvenience, and a lack of specific and clear information	economic incentives/disincentives and regulatory measures for avoiding the use of disposable packaging	demotivated to practice 3R, because they did not believe in an operational and waste collection system	High Quality	
Tong, X., Nikolic, I., Dijkhuizen, B., van den Hoven, M., Minderhoud, M., Wäckerlin, N., Wang, T. & Tao, D.Y.	2018	Quantitative	500 Household analysed in social experience	Incentives helps improve participation rate	A pro-recycling social norm could possibly be built in the neighborhood through local collaboration	are critical for household behaviors change	Encourage strong collaboration among local community, social enterprise, policymakers, and local authority to create synergy for higher participation rate.	High Quality	the opportunities and knowledge to recycle, time for recycling, distance to recycling facilities, and face to face interactions between residents and collection crews are factors to enable effective program
Yazdankhah, Z., Mehrabi, Y., Rakhshanderoo, S., Safari-Moradabadi, A. & Ghaffari, M.	2020	Quantitative	quasi-experimental study of 466 participants (50:50 control and intervention group)	Educational methods uses include poster, pamphlets, training, and messages on various food item	Decrease of nearly half food waste (116g > 76g) after intervention	Training the food service staff is a crucial element to control food waste in this study		High Quality	

See Collation Table ([here](#))

Adapted from the RADAR framework (source credibility) and CASP checklist (methodological quality)

Source Scorecard			CASP - Methodology Quality										Author and Source Credibility					
Author	Year	Title	Screening		Validity of results			Results			Value		Authority			Accuracy		Comments
			Clear statement of research question(s)	Collected data allow analysis of the research question(s)	Appropriate & transparent design to address aims	Appropriate data collection methods	Ethical considerations appropriate	Realistic	Rigorous data analysis applied	Sufficient data presented to support findings	Clear statement of findings	Sources of bias and limitations highlighted and acknowledged	Meaningful contributions to existing knowledge	Authors experts in their field (specialist, affiliated, publications)	Is the journal reputable (e.g. high impact, traditional and alternative outlets)	Potential conflicts of interest declared (e.g. funding sources, competing interests, etc.)	Logical claims and information free of errors and inaccuracies	
Aldoor, M.A. & Moris, J.L.	2021	Paired for change: University students are positively disposed toward food waste diversion and decrease individual food waste after programming	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	This study shows "No Scrap Left Behind" as an effective educational tool which helps decrease 28% of food waste and impact GHG in effort made to food waste.
Altozano, A.	2023	Strategic integration of Solar Energy, Behavior Change, and Recycling Practices in Educational Institutions: A Holistic Framework for Environmental Conservation and Quality Education	Unsure	No	No	No	Yes	Unsure	No	No	No	Yes	Unsure	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Proposed framework on sustainable practices rather than study on the existing educational campaigns. Sample size of 17 FGD on the thought of different policy options, and address education or 2nd priority in policy option.
Benyam, A., Kinney, S. & Hobb, J.	2018	Integrating community perspectives into domestic food waste prevention and diversion policies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Cheruk, K.A., Pappalathan, E., James Barry, J.A., Raju, A.N., Kozlitch, A.E., McQueen, E.P. & Sparks, E.L.	2024	Development of a Community-Driven Waste Reduction Education and Action Program	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	No	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Proposed a 4 level module to high school student in waste education. Survey results that can be used as justification for a clear call for an educational and awareness-raising campaign, highlighting the need for local action.
Chikwano, N.	2021	Factors influencing household waste management practices in Zimbabwe: A community-based social marketing campaign of Pacific University, Oregon	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Use CBM "Greening Oregon" campaign to implement sustainability practices in higher education institute.
Cole, E.J. & Bealman, L.	2013	Recycling, paper reduction, and environmental preferences purchasing	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Cuellar, J.A., Puentes-Ariza, E., Corrao-Galindo, S. & Puentes, M.C.S.	2025	A Community-Based Intervention Proposal for Municipal Solid Waste Management: Analyzing Willingness, Barriers and Spatial Strategies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Highly relevant paper with evidence of reference on systematic review and definition of circular economy.
Gilovic, D. & Bihani, A.	2025	Informing scalability for social innovation: Evidence from a recycling initiative	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Unsure	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Theoretical framework and concept in social innovation aligned with the circular economy with a case analysis of RECLUS.
Goldman, D., Akbari, I. & Amini, A.	2021	Feasibility of a waste treatment facility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Qualitative data on how school educational campaign can influence circular economy.
Kawachi, A., Sores, B.D. & Caporaso-Lucero, K.M.	2025	Plastic Detectives Are Watching Us: Client-Specific Targeted Alternative Single-Use Plastic-Related Behaviour	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Community/school waste education to reduce plastic waste.
O'Donnell, C., Zaman, A. & Brandt, J.C.	2022	The Senses of Container Deposit Schemes: A Case Study in Perth, Western Australia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	CDG program evaluation in Perth and can be highly applicable for DSDG on recommendations.
Sahoo, K.C., Kalpanasudam, J., Singh, S., Singh, S., Parashar, V., Pathak, A., Lundberg, C.L., Rout, K., Akhila, S. & Das, V.	2024	Service providers and program manager perspectives on household waste segregation in Ujjain, India	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Program team perspective on waste management in India.
Nivattanon, V., Mahony, S. & Vivarathorn, C.	2017	Greening of a campus through waste management initiatives: Experience from a higher education institution in Thailand	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Higher Education Program in Thailand on 3R (reduce, reuse, recycle).
Tang, E., Hsieh, L., Dijkhuis, B., van den Broek, M., Widdowson, M., Widdowson, M., Wang, T. & Tao, D.T.	2018	Behaviour change in post-consumer recycling: Applying agent-based modelling in social experiment	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unsure	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Experiment in China with implication for other programs and strong emphasis on local collaboration for successful case.
Yadavskh, Z., Hainda, V., Rasthanderu, S., Solati-Agostinho, A. & Ghaffari, M.	2020	Behavioral approach to food consumption and waste production: A quasi-experimental study	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	

See Scorecard Table ([here](#))

